

The Implications of Language Arts towards Second Language Acquisition and Development of Emotional Intelligence of Learners in ESL Classroom in Malaysia

Nurul Asma Binti Ab Ghani, Dr. Azlina Binti Abdul Aziz

Abstract:-This paper aimed to identify the implications of language arts towards the second language acquisition, SLA of Year 5 pupils in ESL classroom in Malaysia. Aside from that, it is also to see how language arts can indirectly help develop the pupils' emotional intelligence. A quantitative research design has been applied to help achieve these objectives. A questionnaire was used to collect the data from the respondents after the implementation of language arts in the several different lessons. The arts forms used were story, song, poem and chant. The lessons involved a Year 5 class with a number of 40 mixed proficiencies pupils. The school is located in Negeri Sembilan, Malaysia. The results are presented in several tables in this paper to help answer the research questions. The use of frequencies and percentages are employed for easier understanding of the findings. The results from the descriptive statistics reflected that implementing language arts in the lesson can help with the second language acquisition of the learners. It also helps to develop their emotional intelligence in a positive manner.

Keywords:- Language Arts, ESL Classroom, Second Language Acquisition, Emotional Intelligence, & Quantitative Research.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching English as a second language in primary classrooms is not an easy undertaking considering Malaysia is a unique country of multilingual speakers. Teachers are continuously learning and researching the best strategies to effectively teach English to students who are in linguistically diverse classrooms. Therefore, before the Common European Framework of Reference, CEFR was introduced in 2013, the Ministry of Education of Malaysia had first introduced the teaching of language arts as one of the components under the subject of English. Language arts was implemented under the modular of *Kurikulum Sepadu Sekolah Rendah, KSSR* back in 2011. This curriculum adopts a modular structure to the teaching of English which focuses on the development of language skills through fun-filled, activity-based and meaningful experiences (Kementerian Pelajaran Malaysia, 2011). According to Merriam-Webster (n.d), language arts teaches the subjects or skills such as reading, spelling, literature, and composition in which it aims at developing the student's comprehension and capacity for use of written and oral language.

The implementation of language arts in the classrooms are aspired to teach learners more effectively in acquiring English as a second language. Not only that, it is also believed that through the teaching and learning of language arts, it can help to better develop the learners' emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence describes the ability, capacity, skill, or self-perceived ability to identify, assess, and manage the emotions of one's self, of others, and of groups (Serrat, 2017). Serrat (2017) also believes that being emotionally intelligent will help a person to be more successful at what they do as they are able to control themselves well since they are more optimistic and productive. Therefore, this research is carried out to seek understanding of how the use of language arts can help with the second language acquisition as well as the development of emotional intelligence of learners in ESL classrooms.

Learning English as a second language has been made compulsory for all the learners in primary and secondary schools in Malaysia. Learners are to learn English from Year 1 until they are in Form 5 which is a total of 11 years altogether (Adan & Hashim, 2021). With these 11 years of learning English, learners are expected to acquire the language effectively and are able to use the language fluently and hopefully accurately in their daily life both in formal or informal situations. To achieve this aspiration, a lot has been and should be done by teachers in ESL classrooms. One of them is to use language arts in the teaching and learning of English as a second language as what has been aspired by the Ministry of Education, MOE.

Being in a multilingual classroom, teachers face some difficulties in teaching English as the learners speak in their respective native language and just to use one common language which is English is almost impossible especially to learners who live in rural areas. To most of these learners, English is not a second language but it is a foreign language. Therefore, teaching English and getting the learners to efficiently use the language is not easy. Second language acquisition, SLA is strongly influenced by the multilingual learners in the respective classroom (Wright et al., 2017). To show how serious multilingualism can impact the SLA, authorities from the higher level, mainly the Ministry of Education, has to set some policies accordingly to tackle this issue in order to prepare the learners for the betterment of their future at the global level (David & Govindasamy, 2017).

Certainly, it is important for teachers to make use of teaching language arts to efficiently help in the teaching and learning of English as a second language. It can be considered as an approach which ought to be successful in teaching English. With the correct approaches and strategies, learners will be able to receive great support and platform to enable them to learn English easily and effectively (Bayuonget al., 2019). Once the learners are able to acquire the language, it will enable them to use English as lingua franca to communicate to people out of their circle in today's globalized world (Seidlhofer, 2017). Therefore, teachers should continuously make efforts to equip themselves with the correct teaching approaches and strategies to help their learners.

The quote 'one size does not fit all' can be applied in issues pertaining to teaching English as a second language. Up till now, teachers are in a continuous journey in identifying the best methods, approaches and strategies to efficiently teach English. There is no specific method or approach that can be used to effectively teach the four skills of English to learners in ESL classrooms. However, one approach that is deemed the most effective is the use of language arts in helping learners to acquire a second language. Not only that, it can also be used to indirectly help develop learners' emotional intelligence in the classroom with the use of appropriate materials and activities planned by the teachers. Thus, there is a huge need for this paper to research on how the use of language arts can help with the second language acquisition of learners in ESL classrooms and how it can indirectly help with the development of their emotional intelligence.

It is important for teachers to know and understand the impacts of using language arts in the teaching and learning of English as a second language. Thus, this paper serves as a medium for teachers to gain insights and develop understanding of how powerful language arts is in helping learners learn the second language through a fun and meaningful way. While language arts is believed to help the learners academically, teachers need to also know how it can help mold the emotional intelligence of a particular learner indirectly.

This paper aims to achieve two objectives which are;

- To understand how the use of language arts can help with second language acquisition in ESL classrooms.
- To understand how language arts can indirectly develop learners' emotional intelligences.

On the other perspective, these are two questions that this paper attempts to resolve;

- How can language arts help learners in ESL classrooms acquire a second language?
- How can language arts help develop the emotional intelligence of learners?

The findings of this study hopefully will be able to help English teachers especially in Malaysia to understand how the teaching of language arts can greatly benefit in the acquisition of English as a second language. Aside from that,

this study is aimed to provide insights on how language arts can help develop learners' emotional intelligence.

- **English teachers.** It is deemed important for teachers to have deeper knowledge about the implementation of language arts in teaching English as it will help teachers to carry out the lessons in the classroom with suitable and appropriate materials as well as activities. Other than that, with this knowledge, hopefully teachers are encouraged to design more learner-centered activities throughout the lessons and will create a platform for the learners to have autonomy towards their own learning. With the appropriate materials, teachers will also expose their learners to different cultures and situations which will later help them in the development of their emotional intelligence as they are now seeing things from different angles.
- **Learners.** The side who will indirectly and greatly benefit from this knowledge surely are the learners. If their respective English teachers know the importance of language arts and carry out engaging lessons and at the same time utilize the appropriate materials, it would maximize the learners' learning of a second language and develop their emotional intelligence to the highest potential. For instance, when learners read a particular story during the lesson, and they are able to identify with the characters in the story, it can help learners to resolve their own issues by making the characters as the role models. Learners will learn that they are not alone and there's always a way out from some problems if they are willing to try. It will also bud the sense of empathy within themselves.

Carrying out this study is not an easy undertaking. Prior to doing the research, background reading was done to gather some foundation to support this study. However, it was discovered that not much research had been done in the past to seek knowledge pertaining to this issue. Very limited past studies could be used as guidelines and references in completing this research. Reading and gathering the information had to be done in fragments and later on combined together to come up with this whole research.

Other than that, in the middle of the research, some major adjustments needed to be made as the researcher had been transferred to a different school. In particular, Chapter 3 in this paper needed to be redone as the participants had changed entirely. The researcher needed some time to study the background of the participants and also to identify their academic performance especially in their English before the data could be collected and analyzed. There was a vast difference between the original participants and the participants who actually took part in the research.

Aside from that, as this research only included a number of 36 participants from a primary school in an outskirts area, the findings may not reflect to what extent language arts actually impacts the learning of a second language among the pupils in ESL classrooms in Malaysia. Future studies should be made involving a bigger number of participants as well as various locations of the schools. The schools chosen should consist of primary and secondary schools and the locations should be urban, outskirts, and rural

schools as this will help make the findings more useful to all the educators teaching English as a second language at the primary and secondary levels. With the advancement of technology, the survey could be carried out online involving bigger numbers of participants throughout the country.

The conceptual framework is an aid to help researchers to specify and define the concepts that arise and become the root of any study (Luse et al., 2012). It is a necessity to have this conceptual framework as it will provide information to

readers on what is thought to be the construct of this study. Thus, in this conceptual framework, there is one dependent and two independent variables that are identified and will be discussed in this paper. The dependent variable is the implementation of language arts in the teaching of English. Successful implementation of this language arts hopefully will impact the independent variables which are effective second language acquisition and also better development of learners' emotional intelligence.

Fig. 1: Conceptual framework

In the figure above, implementation of language arts in the teaching of English is identified as the independent variable. This variable is what needs to be studied about in order to see the effects it has towards second language acquisition and also the development of emotional intelligence among the learners in ESL classrooms in Malaysia. The arrows in Table 1 above show the impacts of the implementation of language arts towards the learners. It is believed that in order for teachers to plan efficient language arts lessons, they first should know the importance of it and how much impact it can bring towards the learners' learning of a second language. With this knowledge, teachers will be able to plan the most appropriate teaching and learning activities to facilitate learners towards achieving a particular objective throughout the lesson.

The first dependent variable that will be studied is how effective and how optimum the second language acquisition would be if the teachers teach the target language through the component of language arts. Meanwhile, the second dependent variable which is the better development of emotional intelligence is actually the indirect effect of the practice of teaching through language arts. When learning language through language arts, it is undeniable that the lesson will be more fun and it will also create meaningful learning experiences for the learners. Aside from that, positive traits such as optimism, courage, and empathy are parts of emotional intelligence and they are often reflected in the learners' feelings, behaviours, and thoughts (Lake, 2013). All these can be inculcated through the efficient teaching and learning of language arts in the classroom especially when the teachers use the appropriate methods and materials throughout the lesson.

To summarize this chapter, readers are exposed to the introduction of this whole paper. Readers will acquire the overview of why this research has been done. It is believed that this chapter is fairly an important chapter in any paper as the readers will discover the importance and the rationale behind this research. The research questions and the research objectives are what have inspired the writing of this paper. Being an educator, constant efforts need to be made to make sure that the teaching and learning are highly effective to impact the pupils' learning. One way to make sure that educators are doing the right thing is to really know what and why they are teaching and what are the most appropriate teaching methods that they can apply in their teaching. Therefore, it is the researcher's wish that the findings of this paper will provide some helpful insights regarding the particular issue that is being discussed in this paper as this will later help the readers to improve their teaching methods.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this chapter, readers are going to devour the theoretical framework which has been the foundation of this study. Readers are also going to be imposed on the theory of the second language acquisition, SLA. Other than that, the theory of emotional intelligence, EI will also be thoroughly discussed. These two theories are very important parts as they are the foundation of this research. They are also the dependent variables in this study. Aside from that, in this chapter, readers are going to glance through the four language skills consisting of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. This chapter is also going to discuss the teaching and learning of language arts in the classrooms as well as the benefits of it towards the learners.

In any study or research done, it is important to acknowledge the underlying theory/ies that is/are related to the study. The theory/ies discussed in this chapter will be the variables that are going to be observed and studied throughout the timeframe of this research. It is hoped that these theories will be reflected in the findings of this study. These theories are studied because it is believed that they are related to the variables or outcomes from the implementation of the teaching of language arts in the classrooms. These theories are also the representation of existing knowledge related to the area of this study. Theoretical framework is an important part of a study since it provides the structure for the researchers to define the philosophy, epistemology, methodology and analytic in their studies (Grant & Osanloo, 2014).

These theories are selected as the underlying theories of this research after careful selection and consideration. This is following the guideline proposed by Simon and Goes (2011) in which they stated that researchers need to know the main concern for inquiry in their particular study. Researchers also need to note the key variables in the study. After that, sufficient background reading must be done to review current and related literature on this topic. Some constructs and variables that are thought relevant to the topic need to be listed before making the consideration of how the variables are related to the theories chosen.

A. Second Language Acquisition Theory

Hummel (2020) in his book briefly explained that second language acquisition, SLA is a term used to describe the learning of a second language, L2 after the particular individual has acquired their first language, L1. Some individuals learn the language after one another and some learn two or could be more languages at the same time. This can be referred to as bilingual learning. The learning of a second language can happen in formal and informal learning as well as the mixture of both (Saville-Troike & Barto, 2017). They also wrote that if the learning happens in a naturalistic context, it is considered as informal learning while formal learning refers to the teaching and learning inside the classroom with the presence of the teacher and the learners. It is believed that through the teaching of language arts, the learning will take place both in formal and informal ways. Learners will be able to learn the language through authentic materials in a more naturalistic context. As for the formal learning, the presence of teachers will allow them to guide and scaffold the learners in learning the targeted second language.

According to Gass (2013), the study of SLA mainly focuses on how the learners create a new language system. This means that learning a second language is different from learning the first language as the learning happens in a more naturalistic way compared to the second language. When learning their first language, the acquisition happens naturally and spontaneously. Meanwhile, learning a second language requires more effort and involves cognitive skills in processing the new language. They also stated that once a particular individual attempts to acquire a second language, it will enable them to differentiate between what is learned and what is not learned in the new target language. Aside from

that, VanPatten and Benati (2015) believed that the study of SLA is to find answers on the learners and their learning of the second language. It is not really about the teachers and/or their teaching.

Gass et al (2020) in another study proposed that there are a variety of approaches in the SLA. The approaches are;

- Typological approach
- Meaning-based approach
- Cognitive and processing approaches

From these three approaches, the cognitive and processing approach is highly interrelated to this study. For instance, when the teacher uses a particular material on culture, learners need to use their cognitive skills to process the information underlying. This will allow learners to think critically as well as forcing them to understand the language in the first place in order to decipher meaning in the said material. The usage of short literary text in teaching will engage the learners in close readings and to interpret some cultural issues will require the learners to think critically (Scott & Tucker, 2001). Aside from that, they also proposed that the inclusion of learning literature in the second language learning will promote the interpretative skills necessary for literary exploration and also for linguistic production.

B. Emotional Intelligence Theory

According to Boyatzis (2018), the term emotional intelligence, EI can be defined as an ability to recognize, understand, and use emotional information about others that leads to or causes effective or superior performance. Thus, it is believed that learners with better emotional intelligence development will have a better chance at being successful compared to others who do not. Emotional intelligence is believed to help learners achieve success in their academic performance because emotional competencies are interrelated to the intellectual competencies (MacCann et al., 2020).

According to Bar-On (2006), emotional intelligence is divided into five domains. The domains are;

- Intrapersonal competence (self-awareness and self-expression) contains five subscales - self-regard, emotional self-awareness, assertiveness, independence, and self-actualization
- Interpersonal competence (social awareness and interpersonal relationships), contains three subscales - empathy, social responsibility, and interpersonal relationship
- Stress management (emotion management and regulation) contains two subscales - stress tolerance and impulse control
- Adaptability (change management) contains three subscales - reality testing, flexibility, and problem solving
- General mood (self-motivation) contains two subscales - optimism and happiness

It is highly believed that these five domains can be developed through the teaching of language arts in the classrooms. With the correct materials and activities, learners will be exposed to a diversity of stories, songs, poems which

touch on different issues that can help the learners to relate to their own life. Once the learners are able to master all these five domains, it is highly believed that they can be more successful in their life. The imaginative powers of literature may help expand human emotional intelligence for empathy and social judgment (Nussbaum, 1997).

Durlak et al. (2011) strongly proposed that based on Goleman's model of EI, social and emotional learning programs can be the catalyst to boost the academic performance of a learner. MacCann et al. (2020) in their meta-analysis study also discovered that there is ample evidence to link emotional intelligence to academic performance in a positive manner. Through the teaching of language arts, teachers can make the lessons more fun and enjoyable rather than a traditional classroom where learners learn the language in a boring setting. When learners learn based on their intrinsic motivation and interest, it can help to curb the disappointment and boredom of learning in a dull environment thus will result in better academic performance (Pekrun et al., 2010). Thus, it is important for teachers to include the teaching of language arts to teach a second language as it will help the lessons to be more interesting and motivating for the learners to learn better.

C. Language Arts in the Classroom

English language arts education incorporates the teaching and learning of listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills (Donoghue, 2009). This integration of language arts occurs in multiple ways.

- Curriculum, instruction, and assessment reflect the integration of the four skills. The language arts are not perceived as individual content areas, but as one unified subject in which each of the four skills supports the others and enhances the learners' thinking and learning.
- Integration of the teaching and learning of content and process within the curriculum. The common human experiences and the ideas, conflicts, and themes embodied in literature and all oral, written, and visual texts provide a context for the teaching of the processes, skills, and strategies of listening, speaking, reading, and writing.
- Knowledge, skills, and strategies of language arts are integrated throughout the curriculum, enabling learners to solve problems and think critically and creatively in all subject areas. (Donoghue, 2009)

Furthermore, language arts lessons consist of the teaching and learning of four skills. They are oral (listening and speaking), reading, and writing. For the reading as language arts, learners are to read the materials from the children's literature. As for the writing, the focus is on the writing for creativity and motivational strategies rather than the grammatical. While for oral skills, it is to create a platform for creative performance such as doing creative drama or to sing songs for enjoyment (Donoghue, 2009). Teachers need to note that there is a standard that they need to follow when carrying out the language arts curriculum.

Fig. 2: IRA/NCTE Standards for the English Language Arts

Planning a language arts lesson cannot be simply made out of the teacher's interests but needs to follow this guideline as proposed by the IRA/NCTE (1996) as shown in Figure 2.

Through the language arts lessons, teachers are free to explore the materials and activities to be utilised in the ESL classrooms. However, teachers need to note that these materials and activities must be appropriate to the learners' age, culture and belief, as well as their social background. These are very important aspects that need to be taken into

consideration in order to help learners to actively engage throughout the lesson. It is also to enable the learners to be able to identify to the characters in the said materials and later help develop positive attitudes of the learners. For instance, reading a short story in which the storyline is almost similar to what the learners are currently experiencing, will help the learners to find resolution to their own conflict by taking the characters as their role model.

In summary, this chapter discusses the underlying theories that are deemed related to the research questions and research objectives which have been discussed in the previous chapter. This chapter is important as it serves as the foundation of this study. Without discussing the underlying theories, readers will be puzzled as to what made the researcher carry out this study in the first place. Furthermore, without this part, researcher's credibility could be questioned as writing or making a statement without related ground theories can be considered as making a sweeping statement. Thus, this chapter hopefully gives insight to readers as to what are the theories that the researcher wished to study about in depth.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, readers are going to read about the whole research methodology which are; the research design, research participants, instruments, data analysis, data collection procedure, validity and reliability, as well as the summary of this chapter. The methodology is one of the important parts in a research as it serves as the medium in which readers will be imposed on the findings of this study. Without this chapter, readers will not know the findings from this study and it will be pointless to continue reading as it will not provide any significant information to the readers. Thus, readers hopefully will get sufficient data to answer the research questions and to see whether this study has met the objectives of carrying out this particular study.

This research adopts quantitative research design in order to examine the changes in the use of language arts towards the acquisition of a second language and development of emotional intelligence of learners in the ESL classrooms. It is believed that quantitative research can be a valuable tool for answering complex, real-world questions (Tetnowski, 2015). Furthermore, quantitative research incorporates the interpretive and material practices that made a certain phenomenon understandable (Creswell & Poth, 2016). It is important to study certain phenomena as it serves as the platform to better practices in the future. In addition, Denzin and Lincoln (2005) wrote that quantitative research is carried out in a natural setting, while trying to interpret and/or make sense of some phenomena and give meanings to them.

Regarding the use of sampling in quantitative research, any purposeful sampling techniques can be applied. The main objective is to obtain adequate information for the purpose of saturating and analyzing the data. The number of respondents is not solely dependent on specific criteria but rather being fixed by the number of the pupils in one class. A large number of respondents are taken as respondents due to the similarity in terms of compulsory components learned through English. 40 pupils of standard 5 in a primary school in an outskirt area are selected due to their mixed ability and the level of performance which determined by their begotten grades in exam and they share the same obligation, hence the study can access whether the use of language arts will affect the second language acquisition as well as the development of their emotional intelligence. As for the gender, there are 33 male and 7 female pupils in the class.

This research will be using one instrument to collect the data pertaining particularly to the two research questions. The instrument is a type of questionnaire which gives the information needed to examine the changes towards the acquisition of a second language and the development of emotional intelligence.

Questionnaire is used as the only instrument of the research. It was utilized with the hope that a more reliable and accurate response could be obtained from the selected respondents, with the assurance of its confidentiality. Apart from that, the questionnaire is chosen as an instrument to collect data for this study due to its high potential to gather data from a large number of respondents. It is also inexpensive and does not require much effort and time compared to observation and interview. As for the questionnaire, it is adapted from a past research with a similar research objective which has been published. This adaptation is done to make sure that the questionnaire will provide the collected data with validity and reliability. 5 point Likert scale was used in the questionnaire.

The mean score of the answers derived from the distributed questionnaire are calculated and presented in a table. The report of the data analysis are done based on the research question one and two. The analysis provides answers to the research question one and two in this study. For the analysis of the questionnaire, the number of students and percentage for the responses are calculated. The data is presented in a table. Descriptive SPSS analysis is carried out to discover the mean, frequency, and the standard deviation. The results are then used to respond to the research questions. Based on the analysis done, conclusions are made according to the responses to the questions in investigating students' acquisition of the second language and the development of their emotional intelligence.

The instrument is distributed in the classroom among the respondents during English lessons. Therefore, all the data has been gathered at the end of the class. Respondents' opinion and perception are examined and evaluated hence show the effect of language arts toward the acquisition of the second language as well as the development of emotional intelligence.

To create validity and reliability of the data collected, data triangulation has been done.

Triangulation is a central methodology concept and is one of the key features of good research (Cohen & Manion, 1994). In triangulation, the more than one sampling method are applied for the collection of the data. According to this, different datasets will lead to more results and that is why triangulation needs to be done to improve the validity and reliability of a particular study.

When conducting a research or any study, one of the issues that needs to be taken into consideration is the ethical issues. This ethical issue commonly emerges during the collection of the data in the writings (Creswell & Poth, 2016). When planning to do quantitative research, researchers need to prepare themselves for these ethical issues such as privacy and consent. There are three guiding

principles in ethical research. They are; respect for the person or individual of the participant, concern for the welfare of the participants, and justice towards the participants regardless of what feedback they provide to the study, be it negative or positive finding (Creswell & Poth, 2016). They also added that to avoid any ethical issue while undertaking the study, it is important for the researcher to be transparent to the participants by explaining the purpose of the study and not manipulate the data collected in the study.

The research design, data collection procedures, instruments and data analysis coincided with the purpose which has been put forth in the research objectives. The data analysis through the use of descriptive and statistical analysis will deliver the answers corresponding to the research questions and later, the overall conclusion are made based on the findings and discussion. This is very essential in providing a clear outline of this research.

In conclusion, this research describes that the ability to acquire a second language as well as contribute to the development of emotional intelligence is highly related to the implementation of language arts during learning. It is also believed that the immersion of language arts through the learning process helps the acquisition of the language

become much easier thus improving their development of emotional intelligence towards a positive angle. This research is also to give an additional insight or perception towards the approach to the second language as well as the effect of emotional intelligence development.

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

In this entire chapter, the results and the findings of this study are discussed. All 40 pupils responded to the questionnaire which made the response rate is 100 percent. As it has been mentioned earlier, Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) analysis is carried out to discover the mean, standard deviation, and the frequency. The mean and the standard deviation are to see if there is any significant differences between the genders of the pupils to their reactions towards the learning of language arts. Meanwhile, the frequency is to examine the demographic profile of the participants as well as pupils’ reactions towards the language arts lessons.

A. Genders

From the data collected, the analysis of the mean values on males and females variables shows no significant difference.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of responses based on gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Male	33	45.00	3.47
Female	7	44.57	2.51

As shown in Table 1 above, the mean score of male is 45.00 while the female is 44.75. As for the standard deviation, it is 3.47 for male and 2.51 for female. With 0.25 differences in mean score and 0.96 differences in standard deviation, they indicate that the gender of the pupils does not influence their responses.

B. Pupils’ Responses towards Implementation of Language Arts

There are a few distinctive variables going to be discussed in this section as shown in Figure 2 below to help answer research questions one and two.

Statistics

		AbleToLearnNewVocabulary	AbleToHaveWideRangeOfVocabulary	HelpAccessVocabularyOutsideOfTextbook	AbleToLearnGrammarRulesEasily	AbleToDifferentiateTypesOfTensesEasily	DidNotFeelPressureDuringLesson	FeltExcitedDuringLesson	AbleToRelateToTheCharactersInTheStory	AbleToMakeTheCharactersAsRoleModel	ImaginedMyselfToBeInTheStory	LikeToReadStoriesAndListenToSongsInEnglishMore	GoodValuesFoundInTheStories	EnjoyedLanguageArtsLessonsAndActivities
N	Valid	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Fig. 3: 13 Variables Analysed in the SPSS

All the variables are analysed in descriptive statistics to identify the frequency and percentage. As mentioned earlier, the respondents had to choose from five options. However,

according to the data collected, the respondents only chose 3 responses and they are ‘neutral’, ‘agree’, and ‘strongly agree’ as their responses to the items in the questionnaire.

➤ *Able To Learn New Vocabulary*

Table 2: Respondents' Ability to Learn New Vocabulary

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neutral	4	10.0	10.0	10.0
Agree	17	42.5	42.5	52.5
Strongly Agree	19	47.5	47.5	100.0
Valid Total	40	100.0	100.0	

For the first variable, 4 respondents chose 'neutral', 17 chose 'agree', and 19 chose 'strongly agree'. With 'strongly agree' being the highest percentage which is 47.5, it shows

that most respondents agree that they were able to learn new vocabulary through the usage of stories/songs/poems/chants during the language arts lesson.

➤ *Able To Have Wider Range Of Vocabulary*

Table 3: Respondents' Ability to Widen the Range of Vocabulary

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neutral	4	10.0	10.0	10.0
Agree	14	35.0	35.0	45.0
Strongly Agree	22	55.0	55.0	100.0
Valid Total	40	100.0	100.0	

From the table shown, 4 respondents chose 'neutral', 14 of them chose 'agree', and 22 chose 'strongly agree'. With more than 50%, it can be concluded that the respondents

believed that they were able to widen the range of their vocabulary with the implementation of language arts during the lesson.

➤ *Able To Learn Grammar Rules Easily*

Table 4: Respondents' Ability to Learn Grammar Rules Easily

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neutral	6	15.0	15.0	15.0
Agree	11	27.5	27.5	42.5
Strongly Agree	23	57.5	57.5	100.0
Valid Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Another significant finding from the data collected is the respondents' ability to learn grammar easily. 23 out of 40 respondents chose 'strongly agree' making it the highest percentage which is 57.5%. This shows that the respondents unanimously agreed that they were able to easily learn grammar rules compared to traditional lesson employed by the teacher.

According to these three tables, it can be concluded that implementation of language arts in the lesson can help with the pupils' acquisition of a second language effectively. Pupils were able to learn the second language easily as well as in a stress-free environment. This can be seen in table 5 below.

➤ *Did Not Feel Pressure During Lesson*

Table 5: Respondents' Not Feeling under Pressure during Lesson

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neutral	8	20.0	20.0	20.0
Agree	11	27.5	27.5	47.5
Strongly Agree	21	52.5	52.5	100.0
Valid Total	40	100.0	100.0	

The table above displays that pupils felt stress-free when learning English through the usage of stories/songs/poems/chants in the classroom. With 52.5% respondents strongly agreed to the item, it showed that they learn in a stress-free environment as they were able to fully enjoy the lesson.

Moving on to answer research question two, which is how language arts can indirectly help develop emotional intelligence of the pupils, three tables are presented in this section as the representation of the data collected.

➤ *Able To Relate To The Characters In The Story*

Table 6: Respondents' Ability to Relate to the Characters

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	7	17.5	17.5	17.5
Neutral Agree	11	27.5	27.5	45.0
Strongly Agree	22	55.0	55.0	100.0
Valid Total	40	100.0	100.0	

According to the table, the frequency of 'strongly agree' is 22 with 55.0% of percentage. This indicates that the pupils were able to relate to the characters in the story that

they read during the language arts lesson. Meaning that they were able to emphasize to the characters and what the characters are going through in the story.

➤ *Able To Made The Characters As Role Model*

Table 7: Respondents' Ability to Make the Characters as Role Model

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	6	15.0	15.0	15.0
Neutral Agree	12	30.0	30.0	45.0
Strongly Agree	22	55.0	55.0	100.0
Valid Total	40	100.0	100.0	

On the other side, as the pupils were able to relate to the characters, they were also able to consider the characters as their role model. This helped them saw and attempted to resolve particular situation in the same way as what the characters do in the story. This can be seen from table 7 where the percentage of respondents who chose 'strongly agree' is 55.0%.

➤ *Able To Learn Good Values Found In The Story*

Table 8: Respondents' Ability to Learn Good Values

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	7		17.5	17.5
Neutral Agree	13	17.5	32.5	50.0
Strongly Agree	20	32.5	50.0	100.0
Valid Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Another significant finding to answer research question two is displayed in table 8 above. 32.5% respondents agreed and 50.0% strongly agreed that they were able to learn good moral values portrayed in the story that they read for the language arts lesson. With a total of 82.5% of positive responses, it can be concluded that with the right story and activity selected for the lesson, pupils were able to learn the right and the wrong deeds found in the story.

Year 5 in a school in Negeri Sembilan. Data was collected through a questionnaire and all the 40 respondents managed to give their responses. All the data collected was run through the IBM SPSS Statistics version 20. The data was analysed through the descriptive statistics to find the frequencies and percentages.

To summarize, the methodology of this paper has been thoroughly discussed in this chapter. There were 40 respondents consisted of 33 male and 7 female pupils of

As a result, the findings established that the implementation of language arts in the classroom is effective. Research question one which is how can language arts help learners acquire second language has been answered. This can be reflected through the data collected

where the respondents responded positively to all the item in the questionnaire. For the second research question, how can language arts help with the development of emotional intelligence also has been answered through the data collected and analysed.

In other words, it can be said that the implementation of language arts is significantly related to the second language acquisition of the pupils. With the right materials and appropriate teaching and learning activities, it can efficiently help the learners to achieve better result and improve their learning performances.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings of this paper implies that the implementation of language arts in the teaching and learning process is significantly effective in helping learners acquire English as the second language. It is also able to indirectly help develop the learners' emotional intelligence through the proper materials provided and activities carried out in the classroom.

With this findings, hopefully teachers will put more effort to carry out language arts class in the classroom for the learners to optimize their learning in a fun, enjoyable and stress-free environment. More time should be allocated for the learners to explore a new perspective outside of the textbook. This can also help them to explore their hidden potential for creativity and imagination.

Aside from that, with the inclusion of language arts, it will help create more student-centred approach where learners are more responsible towards their own learning. It can also serve as the platform where the learners have more autonomy in the learning process. This can spark the learners' interests to learn English in a positive manners and help build good rapport between the teacher and the learners.

As for the ministry, it is their responsibility to provide proper and sufficient training for the teachers to be better at carrying out the language arts lesson. Aside from that, the ministry should select more appropriate materials that is interesting and suitable to the learners' age and level of proficiency. It is believed that this can also help nurture the learners' interest to read more and explore the imaginative perspective through reading the literary work appropriate to their age.

This can directly advance their proficiency in English.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Adan, D. A., & Hashim, H. (2021). Language Learning Strategies Used by Art School ESL Learners. *Creative Education*, 12, 653-665. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2021.123045>.
- [2.] Bar-On, R. (2000). Emotional and social intelligence: Insights from the Emotional Quotient Inventory. In R. Bar-On & J. D. A. Parker (Eds.) *The handbook of emotional intelligence: Theory, development, assessment, and application at home, school, and in the workplace* (pp.363–388). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- [3.] Bayuon, P. D., Hashim, H., & Yunos, M. M. (2019). Identifying Language Learning Strategies Used by ESL Learners in a Rural Primary School. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education & development*, 4, 151-165. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARPED/v8-i3/6311>.
- [5.] Boyatzis, R. E. (2018). The behavioral level of emotional intelligence and its measurement. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 1438.
- [6.] Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2016). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Sage publications.
- [8.] David, M. K., & Govindasamy, S. (2017). The construction of national identity and globalization in multilingual Malaysia. In *Language policy, culture, and identity in Asian contexts* (pp. 5572). Routledge.
- [9.] Denzin, N., & Lincoln, Y. (2005). Introduction: The Discipline and Practice of Qualitative Research. N. Denzin & y. lincoln (eds.) *The Landscape of Qualitative Research. Theories and Issues*, 1-45.
- [10.] Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2011). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of schoolbased universal interventions. *Child Development*, 82, 405-432. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01564>.
- [11.] Kementerian Pelajaran Malaysia. (2011). *Dokumen Standard Kurikulum Sekolah Rendah. Modul Teras Asas – Bahasa Inggeris SK, Tahun Satu, Dua & Tiga. Bahagian Pembangunan Kurikulum*.
- [12.] Luse, A., Mennecke, B., & Townsend, A. (2012). Selecting a Research Topic: A Framework for Doctoral Students. *International Journal of Doctoral Studies*
- [13.] Gass, S. M. (2013). *Input, interaction, and the second language learner*. Routledge.
- [14.] Gass, S. M., Behney, J., & Plonsky, L. (2020). *Second language acquisition: An introductory course*. Routledge.
- [15.] Grant, C. & Osanloo, A. (2014). *Understanding, Selecting, and Integrating a Theoretical Framework in Dissertation Research: Creating the Blueprint for your 'House'*.
- [17.] *Administrative Issues Journal*, Vol. 4, Issue 2.
- [18.] Hummel, K. M. (2020). *Introducing second language acquisition: Perspectives and practices*.
- [19.] *International Association of Teachers of Reading and National Council of Teachers of English*.
- [20.] (1996). *Standards for the English Language Arts*. Newark, DE & Urbana, IL
- [21.] MacCann, C., Jiang, Y., Brown, L. E., Double, K. S., Bucich, M., & Minbashian, A. (2020). Emotional intelligence predicts academic performance: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 146(2), 150.
- [22.] Merriam, S. B., & Tisdell, E. J. (2015). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. John Wiley & Sons.

- [23.] Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Language arts. In Merriam-Webster.com dictionary. Retrieved May 10, 2022, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/language%20arts>.
- [24.] Nussbaum, M. C. (1997). *Cultivating humanity*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- [25.] Pekrun, R., Goetz, T., Titz, W., & Perry, R. P. (2002). Academic emotions in students' self-regulated learning and achievement: A program of qualitative and quantitative research.
- [26.] Educational Psychologist, 37, 91-105. http://dx.doi.org/10.1207/S15326985EP3702_4Peña-Sarrionandia
- [27.] Saville-Troike, M., & Barto, K. (2017). *Introducing second language acquisition*. Cambridge University Press.
- [28.] Scott, V. M., & Tucker, H. (2001). *SLA and the Literature Classroom: Fostering Dialogues*. Issues in Language Program Direction: A Series of Annual Volumes. Heinle & Heinle, A Division of Thomas Learning, Inc., 25 Thompson Place, Boston, MA 02210.
- [29.] Seidlhofer B. (2017) English as a Lingua Franca and Multilingualism. In: Cenoz J., Gorter D., May S. (eds) *Language Awareness and Multilingualism*. Encyclopedia of Language and Education (3rd ed.). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-02240-6_22.
- [30.] Serrat, O. (2017). Understanding and Developing Emotional Intelligence. In: *Knowledge Solutions*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-0983-9_37.
- [31.] Simon, K.M. & Goes, J. (2011). *Developing a Theoretical Framework*.
- [32.] Tetnowski, J. (2015). Qualitative case study research design. *Perspectives on Fluency and Fluency Disorders*, 25(1), 39-45.
- [33.] VanPatten, B., & Benati, A. G. (2015). *Key terms in second language acquisition*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- [34.] Wright, W. E., Boun, S., & García, O. (2017). *The handbook of bilingual and multilingual education*. John Wiley & Sons.